

Descriptive-turnover

[Code ▾](#)

In this study, we applied a survey instrument to 102 software staffs, 78 have a voluntary turnover.

Data behavior

First we need to look to data behavior and understand what we have.

[Hide](#)

```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  geom_label_repel(aes(label = prop), size=5, show.legend = F, nudge_x = 1) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Turnover")) +  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("TURNOVER")
```

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```

data <- results %>%
  group_by(class) %>%
  count() %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(percentage=`n`/sum(`n`)) %>%
  arrange(percentage)
data$label <- scales::percent(data$percentage)
ggplot(data=data) +
  geom_bar(aes(x="", y=percentage, fill=paste(class," ", round(100*percentage, 1),"
%", sep ="")) , stat="identity", width = 1)+
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Job Position")) +
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("Job Position")

```



```

data <- results %>%
  group_by(age_rate) %>%
  count() %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(percentage=`n`/sum(`n`)) %>%
  arrange(percentage)
data$label <- scales::percent(data$percentage)
ggplot(data=data) +
  geom_bar(aes(x="", y=percentage, fill=paste(age_rate," as ", round(100*percentage
, 1),"%", sep = "")) , stat="identity", width = 1)+
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Age"))+
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("Age")

```



```

data <- results %>%
  group_by(level) %>%
  count() %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(percentage=`n`/sum(`n`)) %>%
  arrange(percentage)
data$label <- scales::percent(data$percentage)
ggplot(data=data) +
  geom_bar(aes(x="", y=percentage, fill=paste(level," ", round(100*percentage, 1),"
%", sep = "")) , stat="identity", width = 1)+
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Study Level"))+
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("Study Level")

```


Most important results of average of aspects: Workexhaustion, jobsatisfaction, taskidentity, autonomy, Feedback, Voluntary Turnover.

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```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Work Exhaustion")) +
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6"))+
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("Work Exhaustion")
```



```
mydf %>%
  arrange(desc(value)) %>%
  mutate(prop = percent(value / sum(value))) -> mydf
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Job Satisfaction"))+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6"))+
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  ggtitle("Job Satisfaction")
```

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```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Task Identity")) +  
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6")) +  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("Task Identity")
```

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```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Autonomy")) +  
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6")) +  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("Autonomy")
```

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```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Job Feedback")) +  
    scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6")) +  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("Job Feedback")
```

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```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Skill Variety")) +  
    scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6")) +  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("Skill Variety")
```

[Hide](#)

```
ggplot(mydf, aes(x = "", y = value, fill = fct_inorder(Group))) +  
  geom_bar(width = 1, stat = "identity") +  
  coord_polar("y", start = 0) +  
  guides(fill = guide_legend(title = "Job Significance"))+  
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("#B22222", "#ffa64d", "#ADD8E6"))+  
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +  
  ggtitle("Job Significance")
```

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```
results <- prepareData()
resultsCor <- results[,3:27]
resultsCor <- cbind(resultsCor, turnover = results[,2])
mediatotal <- asMediaResults(resultsCor)
boxplot(mediatotal$workexhaustion ~ results$class, main = "Work Exhaustion to Job Po
sition",
        las=1,
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

Work Exhaustion to Job Position

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsatisfaction ~ results$class, main = "Job Satisfaction to Job  
Position",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$autonomy ~ results$class, main = "Autonomy to Job Position",
        las=1,
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$feedback ~ results$class, main = "Job Feedback to Job Position",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$taskidentity ~ results$class, main = "Task Identity to Job Position",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$skillvariety ~ results$class, main = "Skill Variety to Job Position",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

Skill Variety to Job Position

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsignificance ~ results$class, main = "Job Significance to Job  
Position",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,3.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

Job Significance to Job Position

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$workexhaustion ~ results$level, main = "Work exhaustion to Level",
        las=1,
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsatisfaction ~ results$level, main = "Job Satisfaction to Level  
1",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$autonomy ~ results$level, main = "Autonomy to Level",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$feedback ~ results$level, main = "Job FeedBack to Level",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsignificance ~ results$level, main = "Job Significance to Level 1",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

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```
boxplot(mediatotal$taskidentity ~ results$level, main = "Task Identity to Level",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$skillvariety ~ results$level, main = "Skill Variety to Level",  
        las=1,  
        xlim=c(0.5,5.5),  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$workexhaustion ~ results$age_rate, main = "Work Exhaustion to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsatisfaction ~ results$age_rate, main = "Job Satisfaction to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$autonomy ~ results$age_rate, main = "Autonomy to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$feedback ~ results$age_rate, main = "Job Feedback to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$jobsignificance ~ results$age_rate, main = "Job Significance to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$taskidentity ~ results$age_rate, main = "Task Identity to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```

[Hide](#)

```
boxplot(mediatotal$skillvariety ~ results$age_rate, main = "Skill Variety to Age",  
        las=1,  
        cex.axis = 0.6)
```


Correlation between motivation aspects and Age

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```
resultsCor <- results[,3:26]
compare_age <- asMediaResults(resultsCor)
compare_age <- cbind(compare_age, Age = results[,29])
sjp.corr(compare_age,decimals=2, na.deletion = "pairwise")
```

some row.names duplicated: 2,3,4,5,6,7,8 --> row.names NOT used
Computing correlation using pearson-method with pairwise-deletion...

Discussion about behavior

We class aspect as negative when index is higher then 3

See the example of scale:

Sentia-me emocionalmente exausto no emprego anterior. 1 = nunca; 2 = algumas vezes por ano ou menos, quase nunca; 3 = uma vez por mês ou menos, raramente; 4 = algumas vezes por mês, as vezes; 5 = uma vez por semana, bastante frequente; 6 = algumas vezes por semana, quase todo tempo; 7 = diariamente.

The folowing aspects seems most critical to movation: Work Exhaustion, Job Satisfaction, Autonomy, Feedback,Task Identity; Showing bigger then 60% negative index.

At the final we can look to cross data in the boxplots, we see that profession have common characteristics and tend to a index like Research that seems less stressful. The level also seems to have common characteristics, showing a negative index bigger than others to job satisfaction, task identity and skill variety.

Descriptive Statistics

Splitting all questions about motivation aspects.

The seven items for motivation:

- Work Exhaustion, when the value is high, I am exhausted from working: q1 ,q2 ,q3 ,q4;

- Job Satisfaction, when the value is high, I am not satisfied with my work: q5, q7, q9;
- Autonomy, when the value is high, I have no autonomy by what I do: q6, q8, q10, q12;
- Feedback, when the value is high, I have no feedback about my activities: q11, q13, q15;
- Job Significance, when the value is high, my job have no significance: q14, q16, q19;
- Task Identity, when the value is high, I do not identify myself with my tasks: q17, q21, q23;
- Skill Variety, when the value is high, I do many repetitive tasks: q18, q20, q22, q24;

We used the **likert** package for extracting a data summary and plots (bar chart and heat map).

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```
title <- "Mativation-related questions"
plot(likertSatisfaction) + ggtitle(title)
```


Hide

```
plot(likertSatisfaction, type="heat", low.color = "white",
     high.color = "blue",
     text.color = "black",
     text.size = 4,
     wrap = 50) + ggtitle(title)
```

Motivation-related questions

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```
resultsCor <- results[,3:26]
KMO(resultsCor)
```

```
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin factor adequacy
Call: KMO(r = resultsCor)
Overall MSA = 0.74
MSA for each item =
  q1  q2  q3  q4  q5  q6  q7  q8  q9  q10  q11  q12  q13  q14  q15  q16  q1
7  q18 q19 q20 q21 q22 q23 q24
0.66 0.69 0.75 0.76 0.80 0.81 0.77 0.60 0.80 0.62 0.62 0.68 0.85 0.63 0.78 0.69 0.7
2 0.79 0.76 0.79 0.72 0.79 0.77 0.76
```

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin show adequation of questions results:

- between 0.60 to 0.69 weak.
- between 0.70 to 0.79 middling.
- between 0.80 to 0.89 meritorious.
- between 0.90 to 1.00 marvelous.

We have many middling index, some meritorios and some weak, so in general we have an adequate sample.

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```
k <- 24
pcacor <- prcomp(resultsCor)
resultsFact <- pcacor$rotation[,1:k] %**% diag(pcacor$sdev[1:k])
colnames(resultsFact) <- paste("Factor",1:k,sep = " ")
plot(resultsFact,pch=20,col="red",xlab="Factor 1", ylab="Factor 2")
text(resultsFact,rownames(resultsFact),adj=1)
```



```
resultsCor <- results[,3:26]
pcacor <- prcomp(resultsCor)
summary(pcacor)
```

Importance of components%:

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8	PC9	PC10	PC11	PC12	PC13	PC14	PC15	PC16	PC17	PC18	PC19	PC20	PC21	PC22	PC23	PC24
Standard deviation	4.8105	3.5182	2.83910	2.45032	2.25244	1.96035	1.93132	1.80474	1.69422	1.47367	1.41510	1.3173	1.28782	1.1465	1.11889									
Proportion of Variance	0.2747	0.1469	0.09568	0.07127	0.06022	0.04562	0.04428	0.03866	0.03407	0.02578	0.02377	0.0206	0.01969	0.0156	0.01486									
Cumulative Proportion	0.2747	0.4216	0.51730	0.58857	0.64879	0.69441	0.73869	0.77735	0.81142	0.83720	0.86097	0.8816	0.90126	0.9169	0.93172									
Standard deviation																1.06136	0.97864	0.95307	0.80606	0.73193	0.70953	0.69529	0.5801	0.50045
Proportion of Variance																0.01337	0.01137	0.01078	0.00771	0.00636	0.00598	0.00574	0.0040	0.00297
Cumulative Proportion																0.94510	0.95646	0.96725	0.97496	0.98132	0.98729	0.99303	0.9970	1.00000

Now, we calculate the internal consistency of all items using Cronbach's alpha, from package psych.

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```
psych::alpha(results[,3:26])
```

Reliability analysis

```
Call: psych::alpha(x = results[, 3:26])
```

```
raw_alpha std.alpha G6(smc) average_r S/N ase mean sd
0.87      0.87      0.94      0.22 6.9 0.021 3.8 0.95
```

```
lower alpha upper      95% confidence boundaries
0.83 0.87 0.91
```

Reliability if an item is dropped:

	raw_alpha	std.alpha	G6(smc)	average_r	S/N	alpha	se
q1	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.6	0.021	
q2	0.88	0.88	0.94	0.23	7.0	0.020	
q3	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.6	0.021	
q4	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.5	0.022	
q5	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.8	0.021	
q6	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.7	0.021	
q7	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.7	0.021	
q8	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.8	0.021	
q9	0.86	0.86	0.94	0.21	6.3	0.023	
q10	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.7	0.021	
q11	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.9	0.021	
q12	0.88	0.88	0.94	0.23	7.0	0.020	
q13	0.86	0.86	0.94	0.22	6.4	0.022	

q14	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.7	0.021
q15	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.4	0.022
q16	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.23	6.8	0.021
q17	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.6	0.022
q18	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.5	0.022
q19	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.5	0.022
q20	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.6	0.022
q21	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.22	6.4	0.022
q22	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.5	0.022
q23	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.6	0.022
q24	0.87	0.87	0.94	0.22	6.5	0.022

Item statistics

	n	raw.r	std.r	r.cor	r.drop	mean	sd
q1	78	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.44	4.0	1.9
q2	78	0.30	0.30	0.29	0.22	4.5	1.8
q3	78	0.51	0.51	0.50	0.45	4.2	1.9
q4	78	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.50	4.2	1.9
q5	78	0.40	0.40	0.36	0.33	4.2	1.8
q6	78	0.47	0.47	0.44	0.40	4.3	1.8
q7	78	0.46	0.45	0.43	0.39	3.6	1.8
q8	78	0.42	0.42	0.41	0.35	3.8	1.9
q9	78	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.66	3.9	1.9
q10	78	0.45	0.46	0.44	0.39	3.9	1.8
q11	78	0.37	0.36	0.32	0.29	4.1	2.0
q12	78	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.22	5.0	1.8
q13	78	0.66	0.65	0.64	0.60	3.5	1.9
q14	78	0.43	0.45	0.44	0.37	2.4	1.6
q15	78	0.62	0.61	0.60	0.56	3.9	1.9
q16	78	0.39	0.41	0.38	0.33	3.1	1.6
q17	78	0.54	0.54	0.51	0.47	4.1	2.1
q18	78	0.60	0.61	0.61	0.55	3.1	1.9
q19	78	0.54	0.56	0.55	0.49	3.1	1.7
q20	78	0.55	0.54	0.53	0.48	3.5	2.1
q21	78	0.64	0.64	0.62	0.59	3.2	1.7
q22	78	0.61	0.60	0.60	0.54	3.2	2.1
q23	78	0.52	0.52	0.49	0.46	3.8	2.0
q24	78	0.60	0.60	0.61	0.55	3.4	1.9

Non missing response frequency for each item

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	miss
q1	0.12	0.14	0.17	0.19	0.13	0.13	0.13	0
q2	0.05	0.12	0.17	0.18	0.15	0.13	0.21	0
q3	0.13	0.06	0.15	0.19	0.23	0.08	0.15	0
q4	0.10	0.14	0.09	0.28	0.13	0.05	0.21	0
q5	0.04	0.19	0.12	0.22	0.15	0.15	0.13	0
q6	0.05	0.18	0.13	0.15	0.17	0.18	0.14	0
q7	0.10	0.23	0.22	0.10	0.14	0.13	0.08	0
q8	0.10	0.24	0.14	0.17	0.10	0.12	0.13	0
q9	0.09	0.21	0.17	0.14	0.17	0.13	0.10	0
q10	0.12	0.10	0.23	0.18	0.14	0.17	0.06	0

```
q11 0.13 0.14 0.15 0.10 0.18 0.14 0.15 0
q12 0.03 0.10 0.06 0.21 0.10 0.22 0.28 0
q13 0.15 0.24 0.18 0.10 0.14 0.09 0.09 0
q14 0.42 0.21 0.14 0.10 0.06 0.05 0.01 0
q15 0.14 0.12 0.19 0.10 0.18 0.19 0.08 0
q16 0.18 0.27 0.14 0.21 0.12 0.06 0.03 0
q17 0.17 0.14 0.12 0.10 0.15 0.17 0.15 0
q18 0.23 0.24 0.17 0.13 0.06 0.10 0.06 0
q19 0.21 0.28 0.13 0.15 0.09 0.13 0.01 0
q20 0.21 0.22 0.13 0.09 0.10 0.17 0.09 0
q21 0.19 0.21 0.22 0.14 0.10 0.10 0.04 0
q22 0.27 0.22 0.15 0.05 0.08 0.15 0.08 0
q23 0.13 0.22 0.13 0.14 0.10 0.15 0.13 0
q24 0.18 0.19 0.19 0.15 0.10 0.10 0.08 0
```

The Cronbach's Alpha more acceptable as good consistency is between 0.8 and 0.9. We can see that all items have alpha equals 0.87, so the alpha has a good value of reliability to our sample.

Inferential Statistics

Let's build the Sample Correlation Matrix, using Spearman rho with average of each factor grouping corresponding questions.

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```
resultsCor <- results[,3:26]
resultsCor <- cbind(resultsCor, turnover = results[,2])
mediatotal <- asMediaResults(resultsCor)
sjp.corr(mediatotal,decimals=2)
```

workexhaustion	0.03	0.03	0.18	0.26*	0.37***	0.38***	
taskidentity	0.34**	0.42***	0.28*	0.51***	0.37***		
jobsatisfaction	0.22	0.33**	0.17	0.41***			
feedback	0.26*	0.43***	0.25*				
autonomy	0.05	0.14					
skillvariety	0.58***						
jobsignificance							
	jobsignificance	skillvariety	autonomy	feedback	jobsatisfaction	taskidentity	workexhaustion

There are only positive correlations, with range 0.00 to 0.57. The most significant correlations are as follows:

- High positive correlation (0.57) between Job Significance and Skill Variety.
- Moderate positive correlation (between 0.38 and 0.49) between Task Identity and Feedback, Task Identity and Skill Variety, Feedback and Skill Variety.
- Weak positive correlation of others below 0.38 .
- No other significant correlation was found with the latter

No strong correlations are observed in general, specially among prediction and any other question. Correlations between survey items are not significant, with the exceptions mentioned above.

Some Conclusions

With factorial analysis, our sample seems yield a meaningful item grouping.

- Each questions collect distinct index, so all questions seems have a important function.
- The classified aspects have little positive correlation;
- The data behavior shows importants details about motivation, can help to understand turnover of professionals.